

VALUABLE

VALORISATION OF FUNGAL BIOMASS USING NOVEL ENZYMATIC TECHNOLOGY

Deliverable No.	D4.3
Deliverable Title	Environmentally friendly produced chitosan
Work Package No.	WP4
Work Package Title	A. nigerbiomass treatment & chitin extraction
Dissemination level	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Public (PU) / <input type="checkbox"/> Sensitive (SEN)
Authors (Name, affiliation, email)	NMBU
Contributing partners	
Due date	29 th February 2024
Submission date	28 th February 2024
Version	1.0
Call ID	HORIZON-CL6-2021-CIRCBIO-01-05
Grant No.	101059786
Type of Action	IA – Innovation Actions
Start date	1 st September 2022
Final date	31 st August 2025

Funded by the
European Union

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon Europe research and innovation programme under grant agreement No 101059786

The present deliverable has already been approved by the European Commission and has been uploaded to VALUABLE's CORDIS website: <https://cordis.europa.eu/project/id/101059786>